

MODELLING OF HEAT TRANSFER AND CONSOLIDATION FOR THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES RESISTANCE WELDING

H. Shi*, I. Fernandez-Villegas, H.E.N. Bersee

Design and Production of Composite Structures, Delft University of Technology, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, The Netherlands

* Corresponding author (H.Shi@tudelft.nl)

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Abstract

In this paper, a processing model for resistance welding of glass fibre reinforced Polyetherimide (GF/PEI) has been developed and evaluated. Transient heat transfer models have been built and the key factors that influence the uniformity of the temperature distribution at the welding interface have been discussed. A consolidation model has been established to predict the quality of the welds, and lap shear testing has been used to validate the model. Model predicted results have been found to compare reasonably well with the experimental results. A non-isothermal degradation kinetic model has been used to find out the upper boundary of the heating time. Based on the present models, a processing window for GF/PEI has been defined, and optimal processing parameters have been found.

1 Introduction

Resistance welding has been researched as a promising joining technique for thermoplastic composites. In order to fast determine and optimise the welding parameters, processing models have become an important tool. Several heat transfer models have been developed by various groups of researchers [1-5]. Most of the models were developed for the welding process of CF/PEEK. Carbone et al. [5] and Stavrov et al. [4] developed finite element thermal models for the resistance welding of GF/PPS. Ageorges et al. [2] proposed a 3-D transient heat transfer model for CF/PEI. Ageorges et al. [3] also developed a consolidation model for resistance welding of thermoplastic composites. In this paper, a processing model was developed for the resistance welding of GF/PEI with stainless steel mesh as the heating element. The

thermal, consolidation and degradation aspects of the welding process were modelled and validated. Based on the processing model, a processing window was determined by using the consolidation and degradation degree as constraints, and a parameters optimization was performed.

2 Experimental

The GF/PEI material used in the present study was supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands. It has an 8-harness satin weave configuration and 32.4%wt resin content. Eight-ply laminates were consolidated in a hot platen press at temperature of 320°C with a consolidation pressure of 2.0 MPa for 10 min. 192mm long and 100mm wide specimens were cut from the laminate before welding. A stainless steel metal mesh was used as a heating element for the welding process, and it was cut into 250mm long and twelve wires wide (about 12.7mm) strips. The mesh had a wire diameter of 0.2mm, opening of 0.858mm and thickness of 0.4mm and was impregnated with 6 layers of 60µm thick neat Ultem PEI resin film.

An in-house developed resistance welding setup[4], was used for the present study. K-type thermocouples were used to monitor the temperature at the weld interface. Single lap shear strength tests according to ASTM D 1002 were used to evaluate the consolidation quality of the welded joints. The test specimens were cut from 192mm-wide welded laminates, and had final dimensions of 187.3mm long, 25.4mm wide, and with an overlap length of 12.7mm. At least six test samples were obtained per welded laminate and hence for every set of welding parameters.

3 Processing Model

3.1 Heat transfer model

Changes in the welding setup, materials and dimensions can have great influence on heat transfer [2]. Therefore, the development and validation of a heat transfer model for the specific welding setup used in this study is a necessary step. 2D transient heat transfer models on lengthwise and crosswise directions were developed to get insight into the temperature distribution along different directions of the joints.

Half models with symmetry boundary conditions ($\partial T / \partial x = 0$) were used to reduce the computational time. The governing equation for heat transfer is as shown below:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \dot{q} + k_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + 2k_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x \partial y} + k_{yy} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}, \quad \dot{q} = \frac{UI}{V} \quad (1)$$

Where \dot{q} is the heat generation rate of the heating element, U is the voltage, I is the current and V is the volume of the material.

The boundary conditions of the lengthwise 2-D model are shown in Fig.1. The boundary conditions at the open surfaces were modelled as free convection to the surrounding air and surface-ambient radiation, as shown below:

$$-n \cdot (-k \nabla T) = h(T_{inf} - T) + \varepsilon \sigma (T_{amb}^4 - T^4) \quad (2)$$

With a free convection coefficient to air $h = 5 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}$ [1], sink temperature $T_{inf} = 20^\circ\text{C}$, surface emissivity $\varepsilon = 0.95$ and the Stefan-Boltzmann constant $\sigma = 5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4$.

Fig.1. Boundary condition of 2-D heat transfer model

The exposed area of the heating element and the adjacent surfaces, shown in Fig.1, were modelled as free convection and surface-to-surface radiation according to the following equations[6]:

$$-n \cdot (-k \nabla T) = h(T_{inf} - T) + \varepsilon(G - \sigma T^4) \quad (3)$$

$$(1 - \varepsilon)G = J_0 - \varepsilon \sigma T^4 \quad (4)$$

Where J_0 is the surface radiosity.

In order to get accurate simulation results, temperature dependent material properties were used for PEI and GF/PEI. The temperature dependent material properties for GF/PEI laminate were measured in DSM Resolve, the Netherlands, and for PEI they were provided by SABIC Innovative Plastics. The physical and thermal properties of the materials used in this study are given in Table.1.

The heat generation from the heating element is defined by joule heating, and a temperature dependent resistance of the heating element was used:

$$P = I^2 \cdot R, \quad R = R_0(1 + \alpha \cdot (T - T_0)) \quad (5)$$

Where R_0 is the initial resistance, α is the temperature coefficient of the resistivity, R is the resistance at any temperature T. In this study, the α value used for the metal mesh heating element was $9.0e-4\text{K}^{-1}$, which was obtained through linear regression of isothermal resistance measurements.

Table1. Material properties for the heat transfer model

Material properties	Density	Specific heat	Thermal conductivity**	
	ρ (Kg/m ³)	C_p (J/Kg·°C)	k_{xx}, k_{yy} (W/m·°C)	k_{zz} (W/m·°C)
Stainless steel	7780	460	10	10
Wood	1242	2400	0.17	0.17
Kapton film	1420	1090	0.12	0.12
GF/PEI	0.49*	0.38*	1945*	1081*
PEI	1270*	1248*	0.22*	0.22*

* Room temperature value

** k_{xz} is zero

3.2 Consolidation model

Consolidation during resistance welding of thermoplastic composites is regarded as a sequential processes consisting of intimate contact and molecular autohesion.

The degree of intimate contact evaluates the ratio of contact area to total surface area. Dara and Loos[7] first proposed an intimate contact model by assuming the surface of a unidirectional prepreg tow as a periodic of rectangular elements. Mantell et al.[8] proposed a modified version of it for time-dependent pressure and temperature (Fig. 2). In this study, Mantell's model was used, and the degree of intimate contact was described hence using the following equation[8]:

$$D_{ic} = \frac{1}{w_0 + b_0} \left[1 + \frac{5P_{app}}{\mu_{mf}} \left(1 + \frac{w_0}{b_0} \right) \left(\frac{a_0}{b_0} \right)^2 t \right]^{1/5} \quad (6)$$

Where μ_{mf} is the temperature dependent viscosity of the resin in the vicinity of the contact area. P_{app} is the applied pressure, a_0 , b_0 and w_0 are geometry parameters of the simplified rectangular element.

Fig.2. A representative model for surface asperities [8]

In order to get a high welding quality, and to avoid de-consolidation and high void content, a constant consolidation pressure of 8bar was used in this study [9, 10]. The region of the contact interface was regarded as mostly neat PEI resin, so the μ_{mf} of a neat PEI plate was measured and used. The μ_{mf} of PEI was fitted by the following Arrhenius equation:

$$\mu_{mf} = 560.03 \exp\left(\frac{247.9}{T - T_g}\right) \quad [Pa \cdot s] \quad (7)$$

The surface roughness of the GF/PEI laminates at the contact region was measured by using a Dektak 150 Surface Profiler. The measured R_a (a_0) was around $0.2\mu m$ while b_0 and w_0 were around $200\mu m$. By putting these values into the model, an unrealistic consolidation degree was obtained, which is probably caused by the too small value of a_0 . Since the laminates were made using a metal mould with a smooth surface, a full intimate contact was assumed to have been achieved.

Autohesion is described as the inter-diffusion of the polymer chains across the interface of two thermoplastic parts brought into contact above the glass temperature of the matrix material [11]. A healing theory given by Wool [12] was used in this study, which is described by the following equations:

$$D_{au} = \frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{\infty}} \propto \left(\frac{t}{t_r}\right)^{1/4}, \quad t_r = B_r \exp\left(\frac{A_r}{T}\right) \quad (8)$$

Where D_{au} is the degree of autohesion, σ is the weld line strength at any time ($t < t_r$), σ_{∞} is the maximum realizable strength, and t_r is the reptation time with $A_r = 59728K^{-1}$, $\ln(B_r) = -105.6s^{-4}$ [12].

For the calculation of the non-isothermal consolidation simulation, a stepwise simulation scheme was used as follows [2]:

$$D_b(n) = \min\left(\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} D_{au}(T_i, t_i), 1\right) \cdot D_{ic} \quad (9)$$

Where $D_{au}(T_i, t_i)$ is the extent of autohesion occurring during step i , T_i and t_i are average temperature and time elapsed during step i , and D_{ic} is equal to 1.

3.3 Degradation model

During the welding process, too high a temperature can lead to resin degradation, which decreases the resin properties and thus the weld quality. In order to ensure that degradation does not occur at the welded joint, a degradation kinetics model was integrated in the processing model to determine the processing window. Huang F. et al. [13] propose a degradation model for PEI with the following degradation equation:

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} = A \cdot (1 - X)^n \cdot e^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (10)$$

where average activation energy, $E_a = 192kJ/mol$, reaction order, $n = 5.33$, and pre-exponential factor, $A = 1.45 \times 10^{12} \text{ min}^{-1}$ [13].

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Temperature model evaluation

Two different power input levels, $60KW/m^2$ and $80KW/m^2$, were applied to the heating element. The power input was kept until the measured temperatures reached a processing temperature of $320^{\circ}C$, then cooling down was carried out by switching off the electrical power. By comparing the measured temperature of welding tests with the model predicted curve, a good agreement was obtained, as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3. Comparison of numerical modelling with the experimental results.

Improving the uniformity of the temperature and avoiding any possible overheating at the welding interface do help improve the welding quality.

Although it is known that the edge effect (higher temperature at the edges of the welding line) could be diminished by using small clamping distance[14], a too small clamping distance could lead to lower temperature and un-welded area at the edges. The lengthwise 2D heat transfer model was used to optimize the clamping distance for the present study. The temperature distribution curves from the edge to the centre of the welding line for five different clamping distances are shown in Fig.4. A 9mm clamping distance was found to be the optimal value that keeps the biggest temperature difference below 10°C for a processing temperature of 350°C.

Fig.4. Temperature distribution by using different clamping distance

In the transverse direction of the weld overlap the temperature distribution is also not uniform because of the different heat transfer conditions between the edge and the centre, as shown in Fig.5. For single lap shear joints, welding quality at the edge is of great importance. The transverse 2D model was used in this study, and different overlap conditions were simulated.

Fig.5. Temperature distribution along the overlap direction

As given in Table.2, five different overlap margin distances were used in the simulation, while a constant value of 13mm was used as the overlap length. The heating conditions were the same for all the simulations, with 60KW/m² as the power input and 104s for the heating time. A 2mm overlap margin, which means the mesh is in total 4mm wider than the overlap area, gave the smallest temperature difference. Consequently, a -2 mm overlap margin, which means that the mesh is 4mm narrower than the overlap, led to the biggest temperature difference. This happens because a bigger part of the un-heated laminates absorbs heat from both edges of the mesh. It must be noted as well that a wider mesh can lead to a significant increase of the overall temperature in the welding interface, so the heating time should be reduced.

Table.2. Different overlap configurations

Overlap margin (mm)	T _{edge} (°C)	T _{middle} (°C)	ΔT (°C)
-2	292	331	38
-1	301	336	35
0	316	346	30
1	338	363	25
2	358	376	18

4.2 Welding quality evaluation

In this study, single lap shear strength testing was used to evaluate the quality of the welds. GF/PEI samples were welded with a power input of 80KW/m² and welding pressure of 8bar, but with different heating times. In order to find out the lap shear strength value of samples with complete consolidation, benchmark samples were manufactured in a hot plates press and milled to the LSS sample geometry [15]. Those welded samples with LSS values above 80% of the LSS of the benchmark samples were regarded as having a good consolidation quality [16]. Therefore the consolidation degree was defined by the following expression:

$$D_{con} = \begin{cases} \frac{LSS_{test}}{LSS_{Benchmark}} & LSS_{test} < 0.8 * LSS_{Benchmark} \\ 1 & LSS_{test} \geq 0.8 * LSS_{Benchmark} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Since the edge of the welded laminates was cut off for the preparation of the LSS specimens, the edge effect was not considered. An average consolidation degree was calculated by nine equally divided points along the overlap direction in the model. The experimental results and the model prediction for different heating times showed a similar trend as it

can be seen in Fig.6. These results showed that a low consolidation degree was achieved when the heating time was below 40s, while nearly full consolidation was obtained with heating times longer than 60s. Cross-section micrographs of samples with different consolidation degrees are shown in Fig.7. The bond line interface can be clearly differentiated in a low consolidation micrograph, while no interface can be seen in samples with a full consolidation.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimental results with the model predicted values for the degree of consolidation

a. Low consolidation (80KW/m², 25s) b. Full consolidation (80KW/m², 60s)

Fig. 7. Different consolidation qualities

4.3 Processing window definition

A full consolidation degree and a degradation degree smaller than 0.1% were selected to define the boundaries of the processing window. For different constant power levels the minimum and maximum heating times were determined to satisfy the conditions above. Fig.8 depicts as an example the selection of a suitable heating time range (from t_1 to t_2) for a power input of 80KW/m².

Fig.8. Acceptable heating time for 80KW/m²

The processing window of GF/PEI for different power inputs was determined and, as shown in Fig.9, it correlated well with a experimental one [10]. Therefore, the processing model was found adequate for the determination of processing windows.

Fig.9. Processing window for GF/PEI

The processing window determined above was used as the design space for the processing parameter optimization. Different objective functions were used in the optimization, such as minimum energy, minimum heating time and minimum power input. In order to minimize the manufacturing cost, minimum energy was selected as the objective function, and it was defined as follows:

$$Energy_{min} (E_{min} = P \cdot t) \quad \text{subject to} \quad \begin{cases} D_{con} = 1 \\ D_{deg} < 0.1\% \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The maximum usable electric current is limited by the power supply unit and sometimes the material of the heating element, so the power input needs to be below a maximum value, P_{max} . Therefore, a minimum heating time was defined by the equation:

$$Time_{min} \quad \text{subject to} \quad \begin{cases} D_{con} = 1 \\ D_{deg} < 0.1\% \\ P < P_{max} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

When the maximum processing time was fixed, a minimum power input was defined by the following equation:

$$Power_{min} \text{ subject to } \begin{cases} D_{con} = 1 \\ D_{deg} < 0.1\% \\ t < t_{max} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

By using different objective functions, various sets of optimal parameters were obtained, shown in Fig.10.

Fig.10. Parameter optimization for GF/PEI

(A is an optimal point for minimum energy; B is an optimal point for minimum heating time when $P_{max} = 80 \text{ KW/m}^2$; C is an optimal point for minimum heating time when $t_{max} = 100 \text{ s}$)

5 Conclusions

A processing model for the resistance welding of GF/PEI was developed and discussed. Temperature measurements and LSS tests were performed to validate the model. The temperature distribution at the welding interface was discussed. A processing window was determined, and welding parameters optimizations were also performed by using different objective functions such as minimum energy, minimum time and minimum power.

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